

AI-PRISM OPEN • ACCESS ALLIANCE

Join an **Alliance of Stakeholders** involved in the development of human-centric manufacturing solutions

Access the latest **AI-powered human-robot collaboration tools**

Take part in an initiative that promotes **resource sharing, knowledge transfer and skills enhancement**

JOIN US!
BECOME A MEMBER!

WE ARE LOOKING FOR YOU

Solution
Developers

Product
Engineers

System
Administrators
& Operators

Infrastructure
providers

End Users
(EU SMEs &
Companies)

If you are ready to collaborate and drive AI-powered,
human-centric innovation in manufacturing

BENEFIT FROM OUR SERVICES!

Capitalisation
of unused
resources

Acceleration
of Upskilling
Talent
acquisition

Early
Experimentation

Test before
Invest

Training &
Certifications

Want to join?

Just contact us at openaccess@aiprism.eu

Visit aiprism.eu/alliance/
to know more

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